

DYMAN

DYNAMICALLY MANAGED SELF-COOLING HPC DATA CENTERS

Deep-Tech

DYMAN is an EIC Pathfinder Project, which proposes revolutionary technological advances focused on the use and management of clean and efficient cooling in data centres.

The previously unproven technology that will be developed in DYMAN will enable the advancement and positioning of European cooling.

Innovations

- ✓ Low-temperature adsorbents that achieve high capacities at very low conduction temperatures below 50 °C.
- ✓ Radically new adsorption heat exchangers made with 3D printed structures that integrate the adsorption material into a porous structure, reducing the internal thermal resistance.
- ✓ Two-phase cooling for high-performance computing servers to handle thermal loads more efficiently from next-generation processors.
- ✓ A revolutionary new type of adsorption cooling system integration in the data centre environment.
- ✓ A new form of active data centre management integrating the cooling system as part of the optimisation of processor management by providing an ontology based on an AI-assisted approach to O&M practices.

Interoperability and Ontology-based approach for Smart HPC systems

Pilots

DYMAN will develop pioneering solutions to reduce the impact of thermal energy management in HCP installations and data server rooms. These solutions will be tested on a virtual commissioning level and a short-term physical test in two HPC facilities: the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (Barcelona, Spain) and the University of Torino (Torino, Italy).

Barcelona Supercomputing Center

- **Location:** Barcelona, Spain
- **Partners involved:** BSC, EAS, IDP, BDTA, SOR
- **DYMAN use cases applications:** Cooling of a central or in-row system

University of Torino

- **Location:** Torino, Italy
- **Partners involved:** UNITO, BDTA, SOR, IQ
- **DYMAN use cases applications:** Cooling of a rack-integrated system

<https://dyman-project.eu/>

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